

"A STUDY OF IMPACT OF ONLINE LEARNING ON STUDENTS OF MUMBAI CITY"

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Abstract :

*Online learning is education that takes place over the Internet. It is often referred to as "E -learning". However, online learning is just one type of "distance learning" -the umbrella term for any learning that takes place across distance and not in a traditional classroom. Online learning means learning through internet. Peoples can get education through youtube, MOOC, Face book, Zoom etc. Pre-Covid 19 period, Teachers and students were completing on line courses due various advantages such as quick access, time saving, flexible timings and repetitive value. Objectives: To study the impact of online learning on students of Mumbai city and to understand which method of learning is better offline or online. Hypotheses of the research study were: H0: Online learning will not replace offline learning in near future.H1: Online learning will replace offline learning in near future.H0: Online learning doesn't provide quick results.H1: Online learning provides quick results.H0: Online learning is not better than offline learning.H1: Online learning is better than offline learning. Research methodology: Primary data was collected from 114 students from different colleges of Mumbai city and Secondary data was collected from books, research papers and websites. Simple Random sampling method and Likerts scale were used for data analysis and interpretations. Limitations of the study were time, money and research data was collected only from 114 students. The research paper will be useful to government to make educational polices and it will be useful to teachers to do further research. 35% respondents were disagree and 35% respondents were neutral when question was asked that online teaching is better than offline teaching. 72% respondents were agree that online learning provides quick exam results. 43% respondents were agree that online learning will replace offline learning in near future. *

Key words: *Learning, MOOC, Coursera, Udemy and Khan Academy.*

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Introduction :

Online learning is catalysing a pedagogical shift in how we teach and learn. There is a shift away from top-down lecturing and passive students to a more interactive, collaborative approach in which students and instructor co-create the learning process. The Instructor's role is changing from the "sage on the stage" to "the guide on the side."

Now a day, Students can learn different course online through different platforms such as Coursera, Udemy, Swayam and Khan Academy. A massive open online course (MOOC) is an online course aimed at unlimited participation and open access via the web. In addition to traditional course materials, such as filmed lectures, readings, and problem sets, many MOOCs provide interactive courses with user forums or social media discussions to support community interactions among students, professors, and teaching assistants (TAs), as well as immediate feedback to quick quizzes and assignments. MOOCs are a recent and widely researched development in distance education, first introduced in 2008 and emerged as a popular mode of learning in 2012.

Objectives:

1. To study the impact of online learning on students of Mumbai city.
2. To understand which method of learning is better offline or online.

Hypotheses:

H0: Online learning will not replace offline learning in near future.

H1: Online learning will replace offline learning in near future.

H0: Online learning doesn't provide quick results.

H1: Online learning provides quick results.

H0: Online learning is not better than offline learning.

H1: Online learning is better than offline learning.

Research Methodology :

Primary data was collected from 114 students from different colleges of Mumbai city through Google forms and Secondary data was collected from books, research papers and websites. Simple Random sampling method and Likerts scale were used for data analysis and interpretations.

Data Analysis and Interpretatio :

Online learning will replace offline learning in near future.

114 responses

Objective	Null Hypothesis	Statistical tool	Result
To study the impact of online learning on students of Mumbai city.	Online learning will not replace offline learning in near future.	Mean 3.20 SD 1.18 Z Score 0.50	Null Hypothesis is fail to reject as Z score is between +1.96 and -1.96 with 95% confidence level.

Online learning provides quick exam results.

114 responses

Objective	Null Hypothesis	Statistical tool	Result
To study the impact of online learning on students of Mumbai city.	Online learning doesn't provide quick results.	Mean 3.77 SD 0.82 Z Score 0.50	Null Hypothesis is fail to reject as Z score is between +1.96 and -1.96 with 95% confidence level.

Online learning is better than offline learning?

114 responses

Objective	Null Hypothesis	Statistical tool	Result
To understand which method of learning is better offline or online.	Online learning is not better than offline learning.	Mean 2.96 SD 0.97 Z Score 0.50	Null Hypothesis is fail to reject as Z score is between +1.96 and -1.96 with 95% confidence level.

Utility of the Study :

The research paper will be useful to government to make educational polices and it will be useful to teachers to do further research.

Limitation of the study :

Limitations of the study were time, money and research data was collected only from 114 students.

Observations and Suggestions :

- 35% respondents were disagree and 35% respondents were neutral when question was asked that online teaching is better than offline teaching.
- 72% respondents were agree that online learning provides quick exam results.
- 43% respondents were agree that online learning will replace offline learning in near future.
- 43% respondents were agree that online learning is good for adhoc courses.
- 57% respondents said YouTube is best for online learning.
- 63% respondents replied they are using You Tube for online learning.

7. Time saving is main advantage of online learning as suggested by 71% respondents.
8. Internet problem is main demerit of online learning as advocated by 85% respondents.

Conclusion:

During Covid -19 period, we have to rely on online learning as we don't have any choice but offline learning is always better as it has face to face contact with students, more flexibility in teaching, two way communication and lectures can be live without any disturbance such as internet problem, costly equipments, self discipline etc.

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